

CURRENT ISSUES RELATED TO THE COLLABORATION BETWEEN SCIENCE, EDUCATION AND PRODUCTION

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Abstract. This article highlights the critical need to enhance collaboration among science, education, and industry, stressing the necessity for substantial reforms to advance higher education and research institutions in our country. It discusses the establishment of new cooperative frameworks with manufacturing companies to create research institutes, establish inter-institutional laboratories, and support small innovative teams based in higher education. The article also underscores the aim to produce high-tech products in partnership with various higher education institutions and the planned recruitment of highly qualified foreign experts. Furthermore, it notes the significant contribution of the research sectors within higher education institutions to the overall scientific capabilities of industrialized nations, including the United States, the European Union, and Japan, and emphasizes the importance of leveraging the experiences of these developed countries to enhance the competitiveness of our economy. The article advocates for stimulating research activities within higher education and increasing their influence on innovative development while suggesting a reevaluation of the research sector's roles and responsibilities.

Key words: integration, innovation, knowledge through science, technology, technopark, university science, practice, competition, foreign experience.

In the past three years, our nation has embarked on extensive and expedited reforms under the Action Strategy. The objective is to align with contemporary developments, modernize all sectors of society, efficiently utilize available opportunities, and create effective implementation mechanisms while adopting best practices from development models. In today's fiercely competitive landscape, fostering an innovative economy is essential for developing export-oriented products and establishing a robust domestic market. Developed nations have strategically

prioritized the cultivation of intellectual resources that drive societal progress. In our country, various initiatives are being implemented to nurture talented youth, modernize educational structures, and enhance the capabilities of higher education institutions. Based on adopted programs, there is a push to increase investments in human capital development, strengthen the integration of education and production, and significantly boost the number of enterprises investing in scientific research. Efforts are being directed toward leveraging existing scientific capabilities and funding for key priority research in economic sectors to address specific challenges, implement new technologies, and maximize the utilization of intellectual capital. The Presidential Resolution of the Republic of Uzbekistan on measures to further advance higher education represents a significant step toward the comprehensive enhancement of this system.

The objective of this study is to establish research institutes in the country, set up inter-university laboratories, and provide support for small innovative creative groups linked to higher education institutions. It aims to promote the development of high technologies through collaboration with other universities and to introduce new cooperative models with high-tech enterprises. Additionally, there are plans to foster a conducive environment for attracting qualified foreign specialists to work in the fields of science and higher education.

The experiences of the past decade in the 21st century indicate that, for leading nations, crucial drivers of economic growth extend beyond mere financial resources and production assets; they also encompass knowledge and innovative ideas that contribute to the creation of intelligent, competitive, and market-ready products. Furthermore, various sectors have emerged where different forms of integration between science and industry flourish, enabling the growth of scientific advancements and collaborative outputs generated by diverse intellects.

The remaining portion of our intellectual capacity will be essential for constructing a new economy and serving as a key driver for success. By implementing a systematic and focused policy that leverages specific legal frameworks and knowledge within the

economy, we can expect to see tangible results in the near future. The establishment of the core components of a national innovation system is vital for transitioning to an innovative economy, encompassing the following elements:

1. Knowledge Restoration Addressing market demands through fundamental and applied research conducted at institutions like the Academy of Sciences of the Republic of Uzbekistan, industry research centers, and universities.

2. Implementation of Research Findings: Integrating scientific and technical outcomes into the testing and production processes of applied research and technological innovations within educational and scientific organizations.

3. Innovative Product Development: Fostering the production of competitive innovative products across industrial and agricultural sectors.

4. Innovation System Infrastructure Development: Establishing the necessary infrastructure to support an effective innovation ecosystem.

5. Personnel Training: Developing a skilled workforce capable of driving innovation initiatives.

Further scientific research has led to enhancements in this structure, incorporating modern frameworks such as: the establishment of new connections in knowledge dissemination; improved education and training pathways; the integration of products and services into production processes; the creation of innovative infrastructure; the development of a market for high-tech products and services; and the establishment of supportive frameworks such as "regulatory assistance," "government support," and "innovation clusters."

Currently, a significant challenge facing the country's innovative development is the "disruption" of the innovation chain, particularly the failure to transition newly developed products to mass production at the industrial level. This challenge is largely attributed to a shortage of specialists who can serve as the vital link between science and industry. Therefore, a crucial aspect of the national innovation system is the

ongoing development of new knowledge as well as the training of personnel, which is of utmost importance.

It is evident that Uzbekistan should consider adopting alternative approaches employed successfully by several countries, integrating these with the goal of generating new knowledge to efficiently tackle national challenges.

The system of education through science encompasses a variety of organizations conducting both fundamental and applied research within Uzbekistan. This is largely facilitated by the Academy of Sciences of the Republic of Uzbekistan, various line ministries, scientific sectors within higher education, and scientific divisions in industrial enterprises and design organizations. The advancement of the science sector in higher education aligns with global trends, and one of the primary motivations for the heightened focus on research within the higher education system is the quest for effective models to cultivate innovative economies in these nations.

However, before moving on to the conclusions on the recommendations for the selection of a key factor in the innovative development of the Uzbek economy, we will consider another important aspect of the problem: it depends on how publicly accepted the proposed model of development. Thus, the above considerations allow us to draw a number of conclusions. As for the main, leading sources of innovative development of the country, the experience of foreign countries and the idea that exists in the Russian scientific community, "academic science or university science" has no clear prospects. As mentioned above, a reasonable combination of both components should, if possible, complement them with the corporate science sector and further intensify the contribution of higher education to the innovative socioeconomic development of Uzbekistan. Thus, along with economic development, it defines three positions: "First, it creates the necessary conditions for scientific and technological progress, the necessary conditions for the development of modern science-based production and advanced technologies; secondly, it serves as a basis for training qualified personnel for all sectors of the national economy; thirdly, one of the promising areas of business activity (sale of patents, licenses, etc.)". In the social development plan, "university

science helps to increase the social activity and demand of the population (primarily intellectuals) has a direct impact on the overall level of culture and education in society. The latter, in turn." that is, it politically reflects the importance of the research sector of the higher education system for society. In addition to describing the importance of the research sector of the higher education system, it should be noted that a number of specific functions of this system have been fulfilled.

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